

Socio-economic Status and Occupational Shift among Badi People in Chhinchu VDC, Surkhet District, Nepal

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Abstract

This study analyzes the socio-economic status and occupational shift among Badi people in Surkhet District. For this purpose, a pre-structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data from one hundred and twelve respondents of age group 15 years and above in Chhinchu VDC. Descriptive analysis has been carried out to describe the socio economic status and occupational shift.

It is found that more than ninety percent of the respondents have the parental property. Almost all of the respondents do not have sufficient food for living. Seventy seven percent of the respondents have knowledge about contraceptives. In case of safe drinking water three fourth of the respondents have safe drinking water. More than three fourth of the respondents are facilitated with electricity. Three fifth percent of respondents are rearing chicken as a major livestock and more than one fifth of respondents are engaged in wages labour. It is also found that sex service among Badi's community is almost rehabilitated but business and foreign employment have been a part of their major occupation.

KEYWORDS: Electricity, Knowledge, Occupation, Property and Socio-economic Status

BACKGROUND

The diverse country being stated as a secular after the revolution in 2063 B.S. has brought peoples' right completely in the hands of their own. However, changes are limited within so called high class based society and those who were under subsistence untouchable and isolated, their question of identity is still in vain. The caste system is the driving force behind the prevalent injustice and exploitation of lower caste minorities in Nepal. Enormous lower caste people still are considered under-privileged and forced to engage in unskilled and manual labour that no other higher caste Nepalese are willing to do.

Nepal's caste system is a part of the caste system of the Indian sub-continent that originated thousands of years ago. Twenty five hundred years ago Gautam Buddha fought against caste-based discrimination, including untouchability, in the Indian subcontinent. Caste system in Nepal began to develop with the restructuring of the Newar society of the Kathmandu Valley by King Jayasthiti Malla in the 14th century. Prime Minister Junga Bahadur Rana, the founder of 104-year long autocratic Rana rule, promulgated the Muluki Ain (National Code) of Nepal in 1854. It divided all the Nepalese people in fourfold caste hierarchy; Tagaddhari

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(Sacred thread wearing or Twice-born); Matawali (Liquor drinking), Pani nachalne choi chhito halnu napame (Water unacceptable but no purification required, if touched or Touchable Low Castes), and Pani nachalne choi chhito halnu parne (Water unacceptable and purification required, if touched or Untouchable Low Castes). The Muluki Ain (National Code of Nepal) of 1963 abolished caste based untouchability, but in practice it remained unchanged. After the People's Movement-I of 1990 and People's Movement-II of 2006, Prime Minister, Cabinet and Parliament/Legislature passed several resolutions to abolish it, but its practice remain unchanged.

Scores of terminologies, including derogatory, in Khas Nepali language are used to refer to Dalits. These include 'paninachalne' (water polluting), 'acchoot' (untouchables), 'avarna,' 'doom,' 'pariganit,' 'tallo jat' (low caste), 'Harijan' (god's children), 'uppechhit' (ignored), 'utpidit' (oppressed), 'pacchadi pareka' (lagging behind), 'downtrodden,' 'oppressed castes,' 'low caste,' 'minorities,' 'excluded group' is stated in the National Dalit Commission's Proposed Bill, 2003.

'Dalit community' refers to communities, who have been left behind in social, economic, educational, political and religious spheres and deprived from human dignity and social justice due to caste based discrimination and untouchability. Dalit is a condition characterized by caste-based discrimination including untouchability. Therefore, the term should be used as long as such discrimination exists. There is no need to use this term when such a condition no more exists. Predominant Hindu Culture has left traditional train zero tolerance about birth that dictates one's placement in society on the basis of colour that goes for both, the constraints and opportunities in the life choices. The burden of the centuries-old caste system is felt disproportionately at the bottom of the social structure, of which Badis form the lowest rung. "Caste-based Untouchability" refers to those communities, who have been discriminated

as water polluting, purification required, if touched, untouchables or any form of discrimination against any community that was identified as untouchable before the promulgation of the New Civil Code, 1963. Badi is a Dalit community from Nepal which belongs to the Indo-aryan ethnic group. According to Hindu caste system this community belongs to the lowest hierarchy. Badi people live mainly in the western part of Nepal. The word 'Badi' means Vadyabadak, one who plays musical instruments, in Sanskrit. Badi is also a common name used throughout the middle-east and Arab region (Pokharel, 1994).

Traditional approach on a word 'Badi' connect its origin that suggests opinions, beliefs vary to the person and their inherited generations in this dispersed phenomenon-one with the next to come. The oldest written corpus in Sanskrit nuances meaning- a word that is often delivered, at the same time, linking its root (ab), that etymons corpus alphabets for the provenance on how it is formed shifting out as 'Badi' later on. Existing written corpus further terms the word compounded 'Bed Bektayam Bachi' which more literally clarifies the meaning-to speak clearly, making it as vital as ever. But whatsoever, one aligns signifies 'Badi' an instrument player (Badi Nandi Kar: Samau one who plays in different occasion, travelling etc. Hence, the basis has an initiative carryout to be more accurate and give feel for how language is being used: 'Badi'-to play a musical instrument; to this end.

Badi girls, from early childhood on, know, and generally accept the fact, that life of prostitution awaits them. Their parents and other Badi, tell them prostitution is, and always has been, the work of their mother in the Badi caste, and that to inspire to another profession would be unrealistic. Badi girls see all the young women around them, and often their own mothers and sisters, prostitute themselves on a daily basis. Indeed, they virtually never see any Badi women engaging in any profession but prostitution. Badi girls also usually do not go to

school, have little contact with outsiders, and, thus, are not exposed to many ideas, values or beliefs that counter those in their own society. Girls also learn early on prostitution is the only means of support available to most Badi families. As Badi girls grow up they learn, from their mothers, sexually mature sisters and Badi women, all about sex and how to dress and act in such a way as to attract men. Within a few months after reaching menarche, Badi girls is being prostituting themselves. So some girls start their own, but most are prompted to being by their parents. A Badi girl's first episode of sexual intercourse is accompanied by a ceremony known as *nathiya kholne*. During *nathya kholne* the man give new clothes, jewellery and a sum of money. Then the girl rub a streak of vermilion powder (known as *sindur*) onto the man's head; and he does the same to her. Then the man and the Badi girl go off by themselves and he deflower her (Pariyar, 1999).

The *nathya kholne* ceremony is similar to Nepalese hindu weddings, where the groom bestows cloths and jewellery on the bride, and exchanges *sindur* with her, before eventually consummating the marriage. Like in tradition Nepalese Hindu marriages, as in *nathiya kholne* the girl is supposed to be virgin. The major difference between *nathya kholne* and Hindu marriage ceremony is that the latter is meant to mark beginning of a lifelong relationship, while in *nathya kholne* the couple usually separates after sexual intercourse, with the Badi girl going on to prostitute her with other men. Mothers play the major role in initiating their daughters into prostitution. In the beginning, mothers often offer the services of their own daughter to prospective clients, and personally handle the bargaining. After months the girl usually feels confident enough to approach client and bargain on her own. Men from all walks of life come to Badi prostitutes as clients. They include engineers, truck driver, teachers, policeman, farmers, students, contractors, agricultural technicians, shopkeepers and hotel owners (Pariyar, 1999).

Poverty is the cause leading sex workers of the Badi community to adopt flesh trade to eke out a living. The historical facts also prove that the so called upper caste people used to use these women sexual satisfaction. Moreover, most of the women working in hotels, motels and industries have been victimized by the bad conduct of their male bosses and seniors. This problem is more severe in city areas than in villages, where so called intellectuals live. Anyone has hardly paid attention to this problem till today's date (Pokharel, 1994).

The transitional point for the upliftment of Badi community has been the next issue that regards their health, educational and economical turmoil. Most of the Badis are still below subsistence level. With neither education nor wealth they have few alternatives but socially sanctioned means of earning a livelihood increasingly requires some level of education which is like one with no legs waiting for an apple with a hope from next being with its bunch up in the tree. Additionally, problem of health facilitated environment has also never been able to receive adequate number of people from Badis spending healthy and prosperous lives as decades has been left behind of their existence. And all these issues and problem emerged due to poverty and ignorance of health situations. Child as well as adult mortality rate is high in comparisons to other caste. Furthermore, unprotected sexual relationship has brought up for insignificant transmission from the disease called AIDS due to the reason being engaged in sex business professionally (Bhattachan, 2007).

The education is yet another field where Badis are again left behind with no opportunities. 'Literacy among Badis is about 10 percent and the community lives at the bottom of the society', according to Executive Director of SAFE who himself comes from the Badi community. There are numerous reasons for they have been deprived of the bright ray of education in the past and even in the present.

Lack of permanent place to stay, temporary source of income that no longer remains consistent, not being aware of education importance, people from non Badi community still having negative opinions about Badi people and in many cases, kids being not accepted in school and educational institution. Again, later Badis themselves being desperate and not being able to confront the present challenges-are something that became the main hindrance for Badis' education (Pariyar, 1999).

The social status of the Badi community is increasingly heading towards under-privileged that have created inequality within the society and its impact on country's progress and its ethnical development along with the way changing society's outlook more than government to recognize Badi as a citizen stands as a major issues in the study. So, for this Chinchhu VDC, it is a place to be worked under as it is also not an exception to it. There had been no research conducted regarding socio-economic status of Badis people in Chinchhu VDC in the past. Therefore, researcher assures this research will be a good specimen in supporting Badi community as their reform is still a long overdue.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literatures dealing with Badi Community are limited. The term 'Badi' is popular subject of inquiry for social scientist. The range of the study about this community varies from the purely descriptive to varying degree of complexities. The importance of this community and its effect on the social norms and values of other communities are inevitable. By studying different facts of their life and way of earning, it may help to formulate the policies related to the 'Badi Community' for policy makers of the country.

Badi are an untouchable Hindu caste with a total population of approximately 17,000 who inhabits in scattered settlement in Salyan, Surkhrt, Rolpa, Rukum, Dailekh, Kailali, Jajarkot, Dang, Banke and Bardiya districts of west Nepal. Badi's main

occupation is fishing (Keeping most of the catch for their own family consumption) and making drums and pipes which they sell to Nepalese in neighbouring communities (Cox, 1993).

The history of 'Badi' is age old. In history, the Badi Community used to serve at kings palaces and rich people or feudal lords' Samanta's house by dancing singing and making some survival instrument mainly Nepali drums called 'Madal' and fishing net (Action Aid, Nepal, Western Region Office Nepalgunj, 1999).

Badi originally came to west Nepal from India back in the fourteenth century, first settling in Salyan and later in Rolpa, Rukum and Jajarkot districts. The Badi's travels often took them out of their home district to as far East as Palpa, Baglung, Pokhara Gorkha and Bandipur (Cox, 1993).

The decision has been made in support to promoting their economic lifestyle along with HIV/AIDS program. In addition to HIV/AIDS program CARL-Nepal has supported the Badi community for food depot program and scholarship to their children. This support has been provided through the group formed by Trained peer Educator who belong to HIV/AIDS awareness and behavior change communication program. SAFE Nepal has next contributed a lot in upliftment of Badis. Initiating to create educational opportunities program for Badi children and freedom from marginalize societal concept for them are some of the major changes they have brought. Similarly, empower to those Badi women with skill training to pursue income generating project is the next indispensable contribution. Due to this, social awareness for women for not steering their kids toward prostitution was also developed.

The first collection published was about the profession that Badi women wanted to change in national daily on 12th November, 2008. It highlighted about Badi women however being engaged in sex profession, they intend to change it

due to their costumer being rare and opportunities also being slow down. Additionally, they have admitted women being more concern about their future and these trains have also led the number being less and dependent on sex as a profession has decreased. Health is the major concern component to address community's strength to work for survival in order to maintain the living standard of life. Health major indicators like child health, Maternal Health and health that relates to different other nutritional health issues focused at different other age group people and the sources to overcome those health related problem has been the big challenges to confront. "It is now well established that the improvements in nutritional status play a key role to improve social living conditions via its influence on improving productivity growth and distribution of consumption among the members of the society. Studies on the relationships between nutrition and productivity suggest that improved nutrition directly increases labor productivity by making workers stronger and more energetic, and indirectly by increasing the productivity of time spent in school, which in term influences long run productivity growth (Behrman, 1993).

Badi Population in Nepal

Badis in Nepal are accounted quantitatively 4,442 in number which is about 0.02% out of total population recorded around 7,000 in figure. On the other hand, an evolutionary, researcher works in culture department at Tribhuvan University, central collage, as per his research has revealed says, Badis in Nepal must be around 6,000 in figure. He further claims the data limits to accuracy because it is a complete research based on the survey done in concerned Badis domiciled area in country's major part during the accomplishment of his academic career. Finally, the "Badi Impasse" highlights the total population of Badi Community across country is around 60,000, the data with yet another with no official verification (Oli, 2062).

Past Socio-economic Lives of Badis

Badi community, in different series of time and even the places have been migrated are the probable reasons they are integrated and considered with different groups, societies and communities. There is a popular act often delivered, "Badis with no surname follows all along breads with no heads." Hence, agreed precisely Badis are identified-Salyani, Falawangi, Sangkoti, Malti, Musikote, Dailekhi, Bajhangi, Achami, Rolpali, etc. This is the way Badis have actually subjected themselves to the different places around the country. Besides, Badis are also known through the surnames of different caste-Brahmin (Bahun), Thakuri, Multami, Gurung, Bhererasaili, Chinal Nepali etc. Badis are exceptional community embedded in patriarchal society practicing generations in behalf of mother. There are various reasons for these things to happen. It is conceivable that Badis people left with a few general socialization in joint family, as opposed to they have started implementing a nuclear family structure in real. It wouldn't be strange to know because of prostitution, lot of Badis connected with different blood group still the father socially remains same. But in the end, father stays in vain whereas mother walks up as a role model for the child's identity and integrates family yet as a joint member. And this vary reason has succeeded women empowerment to some extent where after all those women toiled for family's foundation, lot of time they are destined and anveled in the male dominated society. Train still continues building up Badi women's superiority to step further in their participation to thrive that the whole family has achieved directions what next to sustain because they have been the way where all the financial sources were created. Previously, Badi men were working as makers of musical instruments, their role changed later. Badi men work as support staff for the family sex business as procurers and pimps for their sisters and mothers. Badi sex work is basically a family business and the family is structured around the business. A Badi man can work as a pimp and a mother may negotiate price

until a daughter is old or experienced enough to know the appropriate rates for different customers.

There is no sense of guilt or negative value placed on sexual transaction among the family members as source has revealed from the different community talks made over the places and number of other places where Badis are socially established. So, often Badi rejoice if the girl is born and forlorn if the result is boy. The show off statistical data has never crept up to account the better financial position of Badis in any research found yet. It in an authentic that always remains a bitter truth, these socially oppressed is undergoing a vulnerable situation. In the initial stages, their all the financial requirements used to be fulfill through their profession so called singing and dancing. Low population ratio and monopoly in the field of entertainment workouts had been the main reason they were not being engaged in any other profession after all. But as the time went on, the situation turned out to be worst. And reason for this was, increase in population and not all the time cultural performances being organized. As a result, the amount collected from the profession that tends to offer for better life slowed down. They didn't have enough money and sources to fulfill basic requirements either. Access to promote ongoing situation for that time, people from the places like Salyan, Mushikot, Jajarkot, decided to bail out the Badi community with some rescue package and called it 'Khuwa Tokne' which means bale out rescue package against financial turmoil. It was a provision where a certain village was scrutinized for a period of time and Badis were supposed to go there for begging. This tradition is still practiced in some part of western villages by most of the Badi people. Besides, making (Tabelas, Madal) a drum as mention above and selling it, practicing homeopathic treatment, practicing (padyas)-working on considered bad debts, fishing, etc are some other traditional profession they used to and still do for survival (Cox, 1993).

METHODOLOGY

A pre-structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data from one hundred and twelve respondents of age group 15 years and above in Chhinchu VDC. Descriptive analysis has been carried out to describe the socio economic status and occupational shift. For this study, sample of one hundred and twelve respondents of age group 15 years and above in Chhinchu VDC have been taken. The outputs are shown in frequency table as well as cross tabulation.

This study is entirely based on the primary data. Pre-structured questionnaires were distributed among Badi people. Information obtained from questionnaires is analyzed using various tools. The method of data analysis used in this study consists of tables, simple descriptive statistics.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This is a descriptive study designed to analyze the socio economic status and occupational shift among the badi people in Chinchhu VDC of Surkh District. Based on the information gathered from one hundred and twelve respondents, we have the following results and discussion.

Socio-Economic Status of the Respondents

In socio economic status different social and economic factors (age, sex, occupation, education status and level, family type, marital status and religion, citizenship, marriage, having and own parental property, land registration, knowledge about contraceptives and its uses among them, agriculture, food sufficiency and decision making, annual incomes, saving account, loan and its purposes, electricity, lightening material and fuel for cooking, annual income and kinds of roof) are analyzed.

Age and Sex Composition

Among one hundred and twelve respondents, respondent of age group 45-60 which comprises 32.14 percentages is the highest and respondent of age group 60 and above; which comprises 12.5 percentages is the lowest. About 57 percent of the respondents are male and remaining 43 percent are female.

Table 4.1: Distribution of Ages and Sex of the Respondents

Age group	Frequency	Percentages
15-30	33	29.46
30-45	29	25.89
45-60	36	32.14
60 & Above	14	12.5
Sex		
Male	64	57
Female	48	43
Total	112	100

Occupation and Education Status and Level

Among 112 respondents, 21 percent of respondent are involved in wages labor. Likewise 7 percent in working in other house, 13 percent in agriculture, 9 percent in making musical instrument, 16 percent in foreign employment and business, 7 percent in fishing and 11 percent in collecting sand and stone. It was also found that 43.7 percent of the total respondents are literate and remaining 56.2 percent are illiterate. Among the literate, respondent of primary level, lower secondary level, secondary level, higher secondary and more are 42.85, 28.57, 22.4 and 2.67 percentage respectively. As per the table 4.2 below shows the overwhelming result in the field of education. The reason for this is because of the number of school going children being high. But, along with this, the rate that dominates the drop out ratio is higher which has resulted very low in number for the graduate population. Nevertheless, expectation not always remains mournful. The presented table can also be considered as a step that has started at least with the rays of hope. As we can see, 43.75 percentage belongs to literate and

remaining 56.25 percentage are illiterate, which is the sign of trend that fortunately can bring the good number of people from Badi graduates in the future (Table 4.2).

Table 4.2: Occupation and Education Status and Level

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Working in others house	8	7
Agriculture	15	13
Making musical instrument	10	9
Wages labour	23	21
Foreign employment	18	16
Business	18	16
Fishing	8	7
Collecting sand and stone	12	11
Sex service	0	0
Education Status		
Literate	49	43.75
Illiterate	63	56.25
Education level		
Primary	21	42.85
Lower secondary	14	28.57
SLC	11	22.4
Higher secondary and more	3	6.12
Total	112	100

Family Type, Marital Status and Religion

The selected ward: 7, 8 and 9 however, includes 112 people in total; the leading people structure is followed by 82.14 percentages with nuclear family. The household structure for joint that stands on the second position since to be quite satisfactory as it constitutes 17.85 percent which is almost 65 percent less as compared to nuclear family. Among 112 respondents, 83.03 percentages are married, 12.5 percentages are unmarried and 3.5 percentages are divorced or separated. On the case of religion highest percentages of the respondents belongs to Hindu religion that is 78.57 percentages and 21.43 percentages of respondents belong to Christian (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3: Family Type, Marital Status and Religion

Family Type	Frequency	Percentage
Nuclear	92	82.14
Joint	20	17.85
Marital Status		
Married	93	83.03
Unmarried	14	12.50
Divorced/separated	5	4.46
Religion		
Hindu	88	78.57
Christian	24	21.42
Total	112	100

Citizenship and Ownership on Property

Citizenship and ownership on parental property are the crucial factor affecting standard of living of an individual. According to table 4.4 almost 96 percentages of the total respondents have citizenship which favors the information received from FGD and KII and 4.47 percentage of total respondent do not have citizenship. It is also found that 91 percentage of the respondent have the parental property and almost 9 percentages do not have parental property. Those respondents who owe their parental property in ascending order are others, parents, husband, wife and husband and wife as 37.26, 18.63, 15.68, 14.70 and 13.73 percentages respectively.

Table 4.4: Citizenship and Ownership on Property

Citizenship	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	107	95.53
No	5	4.47
Parental property		
Yes	102	91.07
No	10	8.92
Own parental property		
Husband	16	15.68
Wife	15	14.70
Husband and wife both	14	13.73
Parents	19	18.63
Others	38	37.26
Total	112	100

Land Ownership of the Respondents

Table 4.5 shows that among 112 respondents, 46.6 percentage of respondents have less than one ropan land registered, 28.34 percentages have 1-2 ropan land registered, 21.66 percentages have 2-3 ropan land registered and only 3.33 percentages have 3 ropani and more land registered. It is found that many of the Badi people have some land and have been using for a long time but most of the land are not registered yet.

Table 4.5: Land Ownership of the Respondents

Land	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 ropani	28	46.67
1- 2 ropani	17	28.34
2- 3 ropani	13	21.66
3 ropani and more	2	3.33
Total	60	100

Knowledge about Contraceptives and Its Uses among Them

Table 4.6 depicts that almost 77 percentages of the respondents have knowledge about contraceptives but 50.89 percentages of them are only using those contraceptives and rest of all the respondent are not using any types of contraceptives.

Table 4.6: Knowledge about Contraceptives

Knowledge about Contraceptives	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	86	76.78
No	26	23.21
Using Contraceptives		
Yes	57	50.89
No	55	49.10
Total	112	100

Agriculture, Food Sufficiency and Decision Making

Among 112 respondents, 80.35 percentages of total respondents are involved in agriculture and rest of the respondents are not involved in agriculture.

activities which constitute 19.65 percentages. The major problem of Badi community is that the agricultural product is not sufficient for whole the respondent whole the year and according to them it hardly sustain for 2-4 months (Table 4.7).

Table 4.7: Agriculture, Food Sufficiency and Decision Making

Agriculture	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	90	80.35
No	22	19.64
Food Sufficiency		
Non-sufficient	110	98.21
Decision Making		
Husband	44	39.28
Wife	5	4.46
Husband and wife both	23	20.5
Others	40	35.71
Total	112	100

Conditions of Social Welfare Schemes

Table 4.8 shows that most of the respondents have receipt the help which is 93.75 percentage of total in the form of cash 22.85 percentage, land/building 2.85 percentage and free education 74.28 percentage from NGOs 18.09 percentage, INGOs 2.85 percentage and from Government 79.04 percentage respectively.

Table 4.8: Conditions of Social Welfare Schemes

Receiving Welfare Schemes	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	105	93.75
No	7	6.25
Types of Support		
Cash	24	22.85
Land/ Building	3	2.85
Free education	78	74.28
Sources of Support		
NGOs	19	18.09
INGOs	3	2.85
Government	83	79.04
Total	112	100

Annual Incomes, Saving Account and Loan

According to table 4.9, maximum percentages of respondent that is 59 percentage are earning below Rs 25000 per annum, around 40 percentage of the respondent are earning below Rs 50000 per annum and only one percent of total respondent are just earning more than Rs 50000 and less than Rs 100000 per annum. None of the respondent has saving account. Only 10.7 percentage of the respondent have taken loan for medical checkup, for making gover-gas and for rearing goat and chicken in 1.78, 0.89 and 8.03 percentages respectively and rest of the respondents have not taken loan and that is 89.30 percentages.

Table 4.9: Annual Incomes, Saving Account and Loan

Annual Income Per Annum	Frequency	Percentage
Below 25000	66	58.92
25000- 50000	45	40.17
50000-100000	1	0.89
Saving account		
No	112	100
Loan		
Yes	12	10.70
No	100	89.30
Purpose of loan		
For medical check up	2	1.78
For making gover gas	1	0.89
For rearing goat and chicken	9	8.03
Total	112	100

Condition of Livelihood Assets

Table 4.10 shows that 89.30 percent of the respondents have toilet where 87.5 percent have normal toilet and 12.5 percent have toilet with flush but without safety tank and 10.70 percent do not have toilet. Almost 88.5 percent of the respondents have thatched roof and only 11.5 percent of total respondent have tin roof. In case of safe drinking water 75 percent of the respondent have safe drinking water and remaining 25 percent of the respondent do not have safe drinking water and the

main source of water is tap water which constitutes 42.85 percent and it is followed by well, river and hand pump by 32.15, 24.10, and 0.90 percentages respectively.

Table 4.10: Toilets and Its Type, Nature of Roof, Safe Drinking Water

Having toilet	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	100	89.28
No	12	10.71
Types of toilet		
Normal Temporary	98	87.5
Having flush without safety tank	14	12.5
Types of roof		
Tin roofed	13	11.6
Thatched roofed	99	88.39
Access to safe drinking water		
Yes	84	75
No	28	25
Source of drinking water		
Tap water	48	42.85
Hand pump	1	0.89
Well	36	32.14
River	27	24.1
Total	112	100

Livelihood Status

According to table 4.11, almost 77 percent of the respondents are facilitated with electricity and 23 percent are still not facilitated with electricity so those who are not facilitated with electricity use candle and torch light for lightening their house. About 12.50 percent use Candle and 10.72 percent of them use torch light for lightening. Wood is the main fuel for cooking which constitutes almost 96.5 percent and 3.5 percent of total respondent uses kerosene for cooking.

Table 4.11: Livelihood Status

Access to Electricity	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	86	76.78
No	26	23.21
If not the source of Lightening		
Candle	14	12.5
torch light	12	10.71
Cooking fuel		
Kerosene	4	3.57
Wood	108	96.42
Total	112	100

Trend of Migration

Out of 112 respondents, most of the responder have migrated from Dailekh which constitut about 27.5 percent followed by Awalching, Jajark and Koldada, Rukum and Masina as 20, 16, 12 and 8 percentages respectively (Table 4.12).

Table 4.12: Trend of Migration

Place of Origin	Frequency	Percentage
Jajarkot	18	16
Rukum	14	12.5
Dailekh	31	27.5
Awalching	22	20
Koldada	18	16
Masina	9	8
Total	112	100

Livestock Condition of Respondent

The Chhinchu VDC considered being a village; is most likely that majority of people engaged agriculture because other alternatives are hard being followed for earning purpose. Almost a people pursuing agriculture as their prime source of income however, some people being part engaged other profession to support earning. A agriculture has become the prime source, it is ought to be supposed, people over there keeping livestock as secondary source to increase their income.

level where Chicken covers 60.36 percent as the highest percentages and is followed by Oxen 10.81 percent, goats by 9.90 percent, pigs by 6.30 percent, buffaloes and cow by 5.40 percent and rabbit by 1.80 percent (Table 4.13).

Table 4.13: Livestock Condition of Respondent

Livestock's Description	Total	Percent
Chickens	67	60.36
Buffaloes	6	5.40
Goats	11	9.90
Oxen	12	10.81
Pigs	7	6.30
Cows	6	5.40
Rabbit	2	1.80
Total	111	100

Family Types by Education Level

Table 4.14 depicts that respondent of primary education having nuclear family and joint is 34.69 percentages and 8.16 percentages. In the same way respondent of lower secondary having nuclear and joint is 24.48 percentages and 4.08 percentages, respondent of SLC level having nuclear family and joint family are 20.40 percentages and 2.04 percentages and respondent with higher secondary and more having nuclear and joint are 4.08 percentages and 2.04 percentages respectively.

Table 4.14: Family Types by Education Level

Educational Level	Family type of Respondent		Total (%)
	Nuclear (%)	Joint (%)	
Primary	17(34.69)	4(8.16)	21(42.85)
Lower secondary	12(24.48)	2(4.08)	14(28.57)
SLC	10(20.40)	1(2.04)	11(22.44)
Higher secondary and more	2(4.081)	1(2.04)	3(6.12)
Total	41(83.67)	8(16.32)	49(100)

Knowledge about Contraceptive by Education Level

Table 4.15 shows that 24.5 percentages of the respondents do not have knowledge about contraceptives and 75.5 percentages of them have knowledge about it where primary level having knowledge and not having knowledge are 32.65 precents and 10.20, percentages, lower secondary having knowledge about contraceptives and no knowledge about contraceptives are 22.44 percentages and 6.12 percentages, SLC having knowledge about contraceptives and no knowledge about contraceptives are 14.28 percentages and 8.16 percentages and higher secondary and more all have knowledge about contraceptives which is 6.12 percentages.

Table 4.15: Knowledge about Contraceptive by Education Level

Educational Level	Knowledge about Contraceptive		Total (%)
	Yes (%)	No (%)	
Primary	16(32.65)	5(10.20)	21(42.85)
Lower secondary	11(22.44)	3(6.12)	14(28.57)
SLC	7(14.28)	4(8.16)	11(22.44)
Higher secondary and more	3(6.12)	0(0)	3(6.12)
Total	37(75.5)	8 (24.5)	49(100)

Age Wise Distribution by Sex of the Respondents

Table 4.16 demonstrate that total respondent of age group 60 and above is 12.5 percentage which is the lowest respondent's age group where male constitutes 5.35 percentage and female constitutes 7.14 percentage and age group 45-60 is highest respondent age group.

Table 4.16: Age Wise Distribution by Sex of the Respondents

Age of Respondent	Sex of Respondent		Total (%)
	Male (%)	Female (%)	
15-30	19(16.96)	14(12.5)	33(29.46)
30-45	16(14.28)	13(11.60)	29(25.89)
45-60	23(20.53)	13(11.60)	36(32.14)
60 & Above	6(5.35)	8(7.14)	14(12.5)
Total	64(57.14)	48(42.85)	112(100)

Occupation wise Decision Making in Household Affairs

Table 4.17 shows that 20.5 percentages of the respondent are involved in wages labour where 10.7 percentages of respondent take decision making in household and farming consulting both husband and wife. 39.3 percentages of respondent take decision related to household and farming by husband only, 4.5 percentages by wife only and 56.2 percentages by husband and wife both.

Table 4.17: Occupation and Decision Making in Household Affairs

Occupation of respondent	Decision Making in Household Affairs			Total (%)
	Husband (%)	Wife (%)	Husband and Wife Both (%)	
Business	10(8.9)	0(0)	8(7.1)	18(16.1)
Agriculture	3(2.7)	1(0.9)	11(9.8)	15(13.4)
Wage labour	11(9.8)	0(0)	12(10.7)	23(20.5)
Working in others house	4(3.6)	0(0)	4(3.6)	8(7.1)
Making musical instrument	1(0.9)	1(0.9)	8(7.1)	10(8.9)
Foreign employment	3(2.7)	3(2.7)	12(10.7)	18(16.1)
Fishing	4(3.6)	0(0)	4(3.6)	8(7.1)
Collecting sand and stone	8(7.1)	0(0)	4(3.6)	12(10.7)
Total	44(39.3)	5(4.5)	63(56.2)	112(100)

Occupation of Respondents by Age

Table 4.18 demonstrates that most of the respondent are engaged in wages labour which is 20.5 percentage of total respondent and among them age group of 15-30 years and 45-60 years are highly involved, that is 8 percentages of total. Only few respondents are involved in fishing occupation which covers 7.1 percentages of total respondents.

Table 4.18: Occupation of Respondents by Age

Occupation of Respondent	Age of Respondent in Years				Total (%)
	(15-30) (%)	(30-45) (%)	(45-60) (%)	(60 & Above) (%)	
Business	3 (2.7)	5 (4.5)	7 (6.2)	3 (2.7)	18 (16.1)
Agriculture	5 (4.5)	3(2.7)	4(3.6)	3(2.7)	15(13.4)
Wages labour	9(8.0)	5(4.5)	9(8.0)	0(0)	23(20.5)
Working in others house	2(1.8)	2(1.8)	4(3.6)	0(0)	8(7.1)
Making musical instrument	2(1.8)	1(0.9)	5(4.5)	2(1.8)	10(8.9)
Foreign employment	4(3.6)	8(7.1)	3(2.7)	3(2.7)	18(16.1)
Fishing	4(3.6)	2(1.8)	1(0.9)	1(0.9)	8(7.1)
Collecting sand and stone	4(3.6)	3(2.7)	3(2.7)	2(1.8)	12(10.7)
Total	33(29.46)	29(25.9)	36(32.1)	14(12.5)	112(100.0)

Sex wise Occupation

Table 4.19 depicts that highest percentage of male (20.5) are engaged in wages labour and least percentage (7.1) in fishing. In the same way most percentage of female (16.1) are involve in business and collecting sand and stone (16.1 percent) and at least of them (0.9 percent) are involve in working in others house. Likewise more male respondent are involved in wages labour and few of them are involved in foreign employment and collecting sand and stone.

Table 4.19: Sex Wise Occupations of Respondent

Occupation of Respondent	Sex of Respondent		Total (%)
	Male (%)	Female (%)	
Business	10(8.9)	8(7.1)	18(16.1)
Agriculture	11(9.8)	4(3.6)	15(13.4)
Wage labour	17(15.2)	6(5.4)	23(20.5)
Working in others house	7(6.2)	1(0.9)	8(7.1)
Making musical instrument	6(5.4)	4(3.6)	10(8.9)
Foreign employment	4(3.6)	14(12.5)	18(16.1)
Fishing	5(4.5)	3(2.7)	8(7.1)
Collecting sand and stone	4(3.6)	8(7.1)	12(10.7)
Total	64(57.1)	48(42.9)	112(100)

Changing Shift in Occupation

In this unit changing pattern of occupation with respect to time was described. It also reflects the current major occupation and that of before 15 years. Table 4.20 depicts that there is 9 percentage decreases in occupation related to working in other houses, 2 percentage increases in Agriculture, 4.5 percentage decreases in making musical instrument, 17 percentage increments in wages labour, 16 percentage increment on foreign employment and business, 1.5 percentage increment in fishing, 7 percentage increment in collecting sand and stone and 46 percentage decrement in sex service in comparison to past fifteen years.

Table 4.20: Shifts in Occupation

Occupation	15 years before		Current		Fluctuations Perc.
	Fq.	Perc.	Fq.	Perc.	
Working in others house	18	16	8	7	-9
Agriculture	12	11	15	13	2

Making musical instrument	15	13.5	10	9	4.5
Wages labour	5	4	23	21	17
Foreign employment	0		18	16	16
Business	0		18	16	16
Fishing	6	5.5	8	7	1.5
Collecting sand and stone	5	4	12	11	7
Sex service	51	46	0	0	-46
Total	112	100	112	100	

CONCLUSION

In the view of extreme disparities among country objectives, the situation of Badis at VDC level has remained in darkness. Better rights, better political representative and access average life standard has always been the challenging part to confront. In Chhinchu, as well the situation is not changed with those above explained. The entire study reveals the main hindrance for their social improvement is lack of access to all the resources and rights through which an individual can grow him utilizing them. The main reason that Badis are left behind, when compared with other community is landlessness. Badis in Chhinchu are also facing the unbearable human behavior indicated as one of those untouchables. People from higher caste never provide them to enter in their houses and exclude them in social gatherings. However, few aspects have been changed like sitting together, using the same public facilities etc, but still many changes are still to happen and bring them into practice. Families never have been able to provide the basic requirements for the human development for their kids which have brought the trend for kids of tomorrow being excluded through various means. Amendment of those cultural practices that restores the social dignity and reflects their culture as their identity is what has to be done in order to bring Badis in Chhinchu in main stream of the society.

It is found that more than fifty percent of the respondents are illiterate. More than ninety five percent of the total respondents have citizenship. It is also found that more than ninety percent of the respondents have the parental property. Almost all of the respondents do not have sufficient food for living. Seventy seven percent of the respondents have knowledge about contraceptives but 51 percent of them are only using those contraceptives and are not using any types of contraceptives. In case of safe drinking water three fourth of the respondents have safe drinking water. More than three fourth of the respondents are facilitated with electricity. It is also found that sex service among Badi's community is totally rehabilitated and business as well as foreign employment has been a part of occupation.

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